

Formation Constants of Metal Complexes with Histamine Dihydrochloride

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The complex formation of Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} , Co^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Fe^{III} and UO_2^{II} with histamine dihydrochloride has studied by pH-metric and conductometric measurements at constant ionic strength (0.1 M NaNO_3). Complexation equilibria with Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} have also been studied by differential pulse polarography. It is found that both 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 metal : ligand complexes with histamine forms two complexes with Co^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Ca^{II} and Mg^{II} , whereas with Fe^{III} only 1 : 2 and with UO_2^{II} only 1 : 1 metal : ligand complexes are detected.

The metal complexes of histamine play important part in the biological activity of drugs, and drug action¹. The interaction of metal ions with Hhm and related compounds were investigated by different techniques². However, little is known about the interaction of histamine dihydrochloride (Hhm) with some metals, viz. Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} , Co^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Fe^{III} and UO_2^{II} . This investigation describes the behaviour of these metal ions in presence of histamine by pH-metry, conductometry and polarography.

Results and Discussion

pH-metric studies : Representative titration curves are shown in Fig. 1. Proton-ligand and metal-

ligand constants are presented in Table 1. The order of the stability constants for (1 : 1) metal-to-ligand complexes is $\text{UO}_2^{\text{II}} > \text{Co}^{\text{II}} = \text{Ca}^{\text{II}} > \text{Mg}^{\text{II}} > \text{Zn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Cd}^{\text{II}}$.

TABLE I—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND CONSTANTS WITH HISTAMINE DIHYDROCHLORIDE

Central ion	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$
H^+	8.6	5.6
Co^{II}	5.55	4.80
Zn^{II}	4.95	3.74
Cd^{II}	4.80	3.45
Fe^{III}	—	7.05 ^a
UO_2^{II}	7.5	—
Ca^{II}	5.5	4.3
Mg^{II}	5.15	4.35

^a $\log \beta_2$.

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titration curves of : (a) 0.01 M HNO_3 , (b) a + 0.02 M Hhm, (c) b + 4 mM Ca^{II} , (d) b + 4 mM Mg^{II} , (e) a + 0.01 M Hhm and (f) c + 0.5 mM Fe^{III}

It can be seen from the results that the stoichiometry and the formation constants of only Co^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes with Hhm are in accordance with those reported by Rao and Mathur³. Furthermore, there is a difference in both stoichiometry and formation constant of Fe^{III} -Hhm system compared with the single

system. On the straightline plot of ΔE_p (the shift in peak potential) vs $\log [\text{Cl}^-]$ has a slope of 0.04 giving rise to coordination number of 1.33. The $\log K$ is found to be 2.6 which is higher than that obtained earlier¹. The Cd^{II} -Hhm system is investigated under the conditions identical to the mixed system and the concentration of Cd^{II} ion was kept constant and using different concentrations of Hhm. The results (Fig. 2A) show that peak half-width is 50–60 mV, which indicates that two electrons are consumed in the reduction process and the reaction is reversible (pulse amplitude = 25 mV). From the linear relation between ΔE_p and $\log [\text{Hhm}]$, it is found that 1 : 2 metal : ligand complex is formed with $\log \beta_2 = 8.25$.

Fig. 2. Differential pulse polarograms of $1 \times 10^{-6} M \text{Cd}^{\text{II}}$ in presence of $0.1 M \text{NaNO}_3$ and at different concentrations of histamine dichloride : [A] (a) Cd^{II} alone, (b) $4.695 \times 10^{-3} M$, (c) $9.39 \times 10^{-3} M$, (d) $18.78 \times 10^{-3} M$ and (e) $28.17 \times 10^{-3} M$; [B] (a) Cd^{II} alone, (b) $4.695 \times 10^{-3} M$, (c) $9.39 \times 10^{-3} M$, (d) $14.09 \times 10^{-3} M$, (e) $18.78 \times 10^{-3} M$ and (f) $23.48 M$ Hhm.

report found in the literature⁴, but our results indicate that only 1 : 2 complex was formed.

Conductometric titration of the metal ion with Hhm also indicates the 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 ($M^{\text{n+}} : L$) stoichiometry for Co^{II} , Cd^{II} , Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} and Zn^{II} and 1 : 2 for Fe^{II} and UO_2^{II} complexes.

Differential pulse polarographic studies : The binary complexes of $\text{Cd}^{\text{II}}-\text{Cl}^-$ system are reinvestigated under the conditions similar to that of the mixed

The mixed-ligand complexes formed in the Cd^{II} -Hhm- Cl^- system is investigated (Fig. 2B) by running two sets of experiments, each one at a fixed concentration of the secondary ligand $[\text{Cl}^-]$ (0.05 and 0.1 M) and increasing concentration of the primary ligand [Hhm]. On plotting of ΔE_p vs $\log [\text{Hhm}]$, straight lines were formed in the two cases. The logarithmic values of stability constants are 8.25 and 8.28 in both the cases. Comparing the forgoing results, it is obvious that $\log K$ for Cd^{II} -Hhm, Cd^{II} -Hhm- Cl^- at $[\text{Cl}^-] = 0.05$ and Cd^{II} -Hhm- Cl^- at $[\text{Cl}^-] = 0.1 M$ are identical, thus histamine dihydrochloride acts as a ligand through the histamine base.

Zinc^{II}-histamine system : From our experiments in which only Cl^- ions were used as a ligand, no shift in the peak potential was observed. Accordingly, the ternary complex (Zn -Hhm- Cl^-) is not formed in the experimental conditions. Thus histamine dihydrochloride acts as a simple ligand with zinc ion.

The complex formation between Zn^{II} ion and Hhm in presence of $0.1 M \text{KCl}$ as supporting electrolyte, has been investigated keeping the Zn^{II} ion concentration at $1.0 \times 10^{-6} M$ to which different increments of Hhm were added. The peak half-width of 50–60 mV indicates that the process is reversible and two electrons are consumed, the coordination number being 2. There is a linear relation between ΔE_p and $\log [\text{Hhm}]$ and the apparent $\log K$ is 8.69, which is agreement with the potentiometric data.

Experimental

Calvin-Bjerrum's pH-metric technique as

adopted by Irving and Rossotti⁶ was used to determine the protonation constants of the ligand (histamine) and formation constants of the metal complexes at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ in aqueous solution having a fixed ionic strength $I = 0.1 M$ (NaNO_3) under nitrogen atmosphere.

The pH measurement was carried out on a Corning 60 IA precision research analyzer digital pH meter (ORION). The solutions of Mg^{II} , Ca^{II} , Co^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Fe^{III} and UO_2^{II} as nitrates (AnalaR) were prepared and titrated complexometrically by EDTA⁷. Histamine was obtained as dihydrochloride and used without purification as fresh solutions in double-distilled water.

The following solutions were titrated pH-metrically against standard carbonate-free NaOH (0.472M): (a) 0.01 M HNO_3 , (b) (a) + 0.02 M Hhm, (c) (b) + 4 mM metal nitrate solution (in the case of Fe^{III} , 0.5 mM metal ion was used).

Conductometric titration was carried out using a WPA, C.M. 25 conductivity meter, using an immersion cell at room temperature (25°). Solution (25 cm^3) of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ of each of metal ion was titrated with $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ of ligand solution in 0.5 cm^3 increments.

Polarographic measurement was carried out using

a PAR 264A instrument coupled with a RE 0089 X-Y recorder. The working electrode was a PAR 303 SMDE (static mercury drop electrode) equipped with a platinum auxiliary electrode and a Ag/AgCl saturated KCl reference electrode. The following parameters were maintained : pulse amplitude, 25 mV; drop time, 1 s; scan rate, 2 mV s^{-1} . For the removal of dissolved oxygen, pure nitrogen was bubbled through the solution for 20 min.

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